

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KOFFI****FIRST NAME: GERMAIN****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
2. American vs British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
3. Punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
4. Write a good academic essay (EUCLID 2024, 6-12)
5. A style guide (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)

WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

After three months of hesitation, mainly due to the language of the courses (which is English), I finally decided to embrace this exciting adventure. Dr. Gulma's first email of welcome and encouragement profoundly changed my vision of the program, so motivating were his words.

Today, aboard this great ship of knowledge, I am about to carry out a very important exercise: writing a response paper. Since, for me, one of the keys to success lies in continuous reading and learning, I have meticulously taken the time to read and re-read all the documents made available to me at the start of the program. I also repeatedly watched the various videos posted on the platform, which were unfailingly useful.

While reading these documents and watching these videos, I have noted that a lot of attention and seriousness must be devoted to this training process if one desires to emerge victorious from this competition.

Also, as mentioned at the beginning, I am fully aware of the enormous efforts required to improve my level of English. This is essential not only to be able to understand the courses and pass the exams, but also for my future professional career as a doctor.

In this Response Paper, I will set out to select five key topics from the ACA-401/401D course pack for period one, which I will summarize in my own words and understanding, while respecting EUCLID University's requirements. The five topics are plagiarism, American vs. British English, punctuation, writing a good academic essay, and style guide.

2) PLAGIARISM

Giving To Whom It May Concern is a mark of honesty and deserves to be adopted by all for a better world. Jesus even said (Matthew 22-21): "Give to Caesar what is Caesar's, and to God what is God's."

Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2024, 34). From reading the course material, I was able to learn that plagiarism is a serious academic offense and deserves to be absolutely avoided.

I believe that the road to obtaining a Ph.D. at EUCLID University is a narrow one (governed by strict operating rules) and requires meticulous and honest people. That is why this university has set out to explain the concept of plagiarism, its consequences on our academic career and the various ways of avoiding it.

According to EUCLID (2024, 34) to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using. If I, as a student, can adhere strictly to the advice given by EUCLID, I will also be able to avoid plagiarism and produce quality documents.

3) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

Although I was not born in an English-speaking country, I did learn in high school that there were some differences between American and British English. For me, these differences were more significant and numerous than the similarities.

Through ACA-401D course pack period one I realized that these two types of English are more similar than different, especially with "educated" or "scientific" English. And that most of the divergences can be attributed to different national histories and cultural developments (cf. Are Americans Ruining English? [PBS]) and how the two national variants have changed as a result (EUCLID 2024, 25).

I also learned that EUCLID does not impose either of these two types of English on students as they pursue their academic careers. However, it requires students to specify at the start of a Response Paper the type of English they wish to use and to respect the applicable rules. This flexibility is encouraging and objective, as it allows students to use the type of English they feel most familiar and comfortable with.

Having lived and worked in Liberia for over two years, I have realized (through the ACA-401D course pack period one) that Liberia uses mainly the American version in both written and spoken English. I feel quite comfortable using this English for the rest of my academic career and will endeavor to apply the requirements of this type of English in all my writings. However, I am quite aware of the extra effort required to correctly apply the rules of American English in my writing, given that I am not a native of an English-speaking country and that I learned English during my studies and my professional career. Far from being a handicap, this reality is a challenge and a real source of motivation for me.

4) PUNCTUATION

One anecdote tells of a king who, during a tribal war, used the same phrase to execute or rescue a prisoner. The phrase was: "*Tuer pas laisser passer*." Only the position of the comma indicated the action to be performed. Thus, "*Tuer pas, laisser passer*." meant freeing the prisoner, while "*Tuer, pas laisser passer*." meant the opposite. This anecdote illustrates the importance of punctuation in writing, and its usefulness in enhancing reader comprehension.

Use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence (EUCLID 2024, 16) helps me understand that punctuation (no matter how small), if misplaced, can change the meaning of an entire sentence.

I am going to use a practical example from ACA-401D course pack period one to support what I have understood about punctuation and its ability to confuse certain statements. In the following sentence: "**I used to be slim: I will try to lose weight**", there is no direct logic linking the two statements. In fact, just because one has put on weight does not mean one should lose weight if this person aim is not to regain his/her former shape. However, in this expression: "**I would like to be slim: I will try to lose weight**", the relationship between losing weight and becoming slim is obvious. In this way, I was able to understand that a person's ability to use the right punctuation starts with his or her ability to make a logical connection between different facts.

With the punctuation rules, the student has a clear idea of how to punctuate according to the type of English used to write his document. As Dr. Gulma mentioned in his comment on the response paper review example, "In US English, punctuations are placed before closing the inverted comma except if a citation follows immediately" (EUCLID 2024, 68). From this commentary, I realized that punctuation might differ if one uses American or British English.

5) WRITE A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

To be a good academic writer, one needs to comply with the writing rules required by the institution in which one is pursuing his/her course. For this reason, EUCLID has

taken the time to explain its writing rules extensively in the first part of the ACA-401D course pack and a 14-minute video posted on its platform.

For me, the most important thing to know is that the structure accepted by EUCLID when writing an academic essay should include an introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 10). While the introduction moves from general to specific and gives a brief description of the subject, the conclusion moves from specific to general, summarizing the essential points of the subject and including a final statement. The body of the subject, made up of paragraphs, responds to the problem of the subject using relevant examples and authoritative quotes (EUCLID 2024, 10).

Reading the ACA-401D course material, I understand that the introduction and conclusion should be written after the body. This information contradicts my past knowledge, which encourages the opposite. However, following the explanation given by EUCLID, I find this statement very logical to be adopted. Indeed, after the body has been written, it will be easier and more efficient to write the introduction and conclusion since, in the body, the writer has taken the time to unravel all the mysteries of the subject at hand.

As an academic essay is aimed at answering a question or specific task, the writer should always keep in mind the topic and its scope to avoid taking it out of context and using it as a pretext. That is why EUCLID advises the student to do a lot of research on the subject before starting writing. This does not mean procrastinating, either, as there is a saying that anyone who puts things off until tomorrow will meet with misfortune. Starting as early as possible is what EUCLID recommends: "it is best to start early as possible. One the initial things is to have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write. It is never advisable to procrastinate" (EUCLID 2024, 7).

I believe that by following the advice and recommendations from EUCLID, one can easily write a good academic essay. However, this does not prevent the writer from submitting his work to an adequate person (especially someone who has a better grasp of the subject) for reading and comment before submitting it to the validator.

6) A STYLE GUIDE

Euclid University's flexibility on certain subjects makes its training program interesting and encouraging. For example, EUCLID recommends (but does not impose) the Chicago Rules (Turabian). Consequently, the usage of other internationally recognized rules remains fine.

According to EUCLID (2024, 41), a style guide is "a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent." I have learned that adopting a style guide when writing is essential to ensure consistency. Even if many creative writers minimize the need for a style guide, I believe that adopting one is essential, especially for beginners like me, who must write in standard English, which is not my mother tongue. I, therefore, find it salutary that EUCLID recommends Turabian

and makes it available to its students. This document deserves to be exploited and taken as a compass for the consistency of my essays.

I have also learned from (EUCLID 2024, 41) that the lack of a single authoritative source on style for written English means that there is, and will always be, a certain amount of debate on elements of style. For me, these debates should be utilitarian and enriching rather than divisive, for just as gold is tested by fire, human writing must be subject to criticism and comment to ensure its consistency and veracity.

7) CONCLUSION

This first introductory course, ACA-401/401D, has been extremely useful not only for my PhD studies in Climate Change and Sustainability but also for my professional career. Indeed, this course and the various associated videos guide the student that I am in writing a consistent and relevant article. Above all, it helped me to deconstruct some of the false beliefs I had inherited from my past training courses on certain crucial subjects concerning academic writing.

This salutary course pack really helped me understand that one should devote enough time to researching a subject before starting to write about it while avoiding procrastination. While writing, one should, above all, keep in mind the subject and its field of action to avoid taking it out of context and submit the document to a close person (preferably a professional in the field concerned) for reading before submission to the validator.

I believe that this invaluable document will be my ideal companion throughout my time with EUCLID and for the rest of my professional career. I, therefore, pledge to read and reread it as many times as possible to master it because mastering it will be essential for the rest of my career.

REFERENCES

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